

Marketing Strategies in the Implementation of Product Sells in Small Company: Cases Studies in Company Amaaraa.Id

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ABSTRACT: This study attempts to determine the best marketing plan for boosting product sales turnover at the Amaaraa.id company in Makassar City. Observations, interviews, and documentation of research objects are utilized as data gathering techniques in the qualitative descriptive research approach. The data is then analysed using SWOT analysis. According to the research's findings, the Amaaraa.id Enterprise's turn-around plan in the city of Makassar is based on SWOT assessments that are in Quadrant III. Companies have good prospects, but they also have internal flaws that they can address by changing their tactics. Thus, this approach enables continued expansion, increased growth, and maximal advancement.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Strategy, SWOT analysis, Small business.

INTRODUCTION

Small businesses could benefit from using social media to sell their goods and services. Small businesses can engage in marketing activities like product introductions, creating communication with present and new customers, and growing business networks through social media. Small businesses can use social media, such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Whatsapp, etc., to communicate and share information with their present and potential customers without regard to geography (Anjani et al., 2018). Small businesses can market their goods through social networks by sharing information about the most recent business activities, sharing in-depth and expansive product images, developing digital products, connecting with potential customers, and growing their trade network (Rakib et al., 2018).

Due to the fact that the sole capital necessary for these firms is Online expenses. It is envisaged that by doing this, marketing products intended for small enterprises won't present a challenge. With social media, business owners no longer struggle to find reliable and pertinent information for their operations (Irfan, 2014). Instead, they can do it easily. The Internet has changed from being a tool for social network-based information exchange to a tool for strategic marketing applications like marketing, sales, and customer service (Sumarsid & Paryanti, 2022). Overall, social media marketing has the advantage of having a lot of potential for corporate use (Afrilia, 2018). Social networks are used in business as a tool for business communication, assisting in the promotion of goods and services, facilitating communication with clients and suppliers, introducing brands, and reducing costs and for the purpose of online sales.

Objective

The objective of how marketing strategies (product, price, location, and promotion) in increasing product sales turnover on Amaaraa.id enterprise in Makassar city.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Entrepreneurship

The study of values, skills, and conduct in the face of challenges in life is known as entrepreneurship (Fatimah et al., 2020). Because of its intact and real body of knowledge, two concepts venture start-up and venture growth and unique object the capacity to create enterprise is taught as a single discipline. (Syam, 2017). An entrepreneur always has and works to improve his talents in accordance with the theory (Rakib, 2016) that an entrepreneur who wants to be successful in managing and boosting his business performance must have good communication skills. An entrepreneur is also someone who launches a new business despite all the dangers and unknowns in an effort to profit and expand their firm (Aini & Oktafani, 2020).

2. Strategy

According to Cahyono (2016), a strategy is a long-term plan that is followed by activities intended to achieve a particular goal, which is typically "victory". A strategy is a plan that we will carry out over the long run as well as the short term, as we can see. A firm can run smoothly, be directed, and execute effective and proper marketing to maximize sales in order to the company's mission to dominate the market. This is in addition to having a strategy (Latief, 2019).

3. Marketing

According to Assauri (2015), marketing is the single most important aspect of business life since companies work hard to achieve their goals of starting a business, making money, and ensuring that they are continuing to live happily. Marketing, in the opinion of Assauri (2014) is the gathering of vendors and buyers to conduct transactions involving commodities or services. As a result, the term "market" no longer refers to a specific location but rather to a process or activity that involves meeting sellers and buyers while presenting a product to customers. The definition of marketing states that it is a technique for identifying consumer demand for products or services in order to satisfy customers and achieve business objectives (Akrimi & Khemakem, 2012).

4. Marketing Strategy

A marketing strategy is a plan that spreads company expectations about the impact of various actions or marketing programs on the demand for products or product lines of a certain target market, according to (Amstrong, 2016). A fascinating program involves marketing activities that can change prices, alter advertising campaigns, create unique promotions, choose distribution methods, and other things that can affect consumer demand for items. The definition of marketing strategy, according to (Rakib et al., 2020) is a decision pattern within a company that defines and discloses a goal, intent, or goal that produces primary wisdom and plans for the achievement of a goal as well as detail the scope of the business that the company will pursue. A marketing strategy, according to Untari & Fajariana (2018) is something that is really vital for any organization. vital things are typically difficult to develop and put into practice, necessitating a series of in-depth analyses to minimize any uncertainties or risks. Marketing strategy is defined in Varadarajan (2015), p. 128 as follows: The integrated set of decisions made by an organization that determines the key markets to serve, market segments to target, marketing activities to carry out, how to carry them out, and how to allocate marketing resources among markets, market segments, and marketing activities in order to develop, communicate, and deliver a product that adds value to customers in interactions with the organization and enables the organization to grow (Hermawan, 2012).

5. Sales turnover

Every marketing or sale, according to the Dharmmesta & Handoko (2013), has a primary goal, which is to achieve a distribution known as a sales turnover. If the return on sales exceeds the capital, the sales turnover is said to be profitable; if the result is less than the capital, it is said to be unprofitable. The sustainability of a business is significantly impacted by sales turnover. If the company's sales turnover keeps increasing or remaining consistent, it will prosper and survive. Sales turnover is the total amount of sales activities for a product of goods and services that have been constantly or in one accounting process over a specific period of time.

6. SWOT Analysis

SWOT evaluates strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, in accordance with Widagdha et al., (2018). To find opportunities and threats in the now and the future, strengths and weaknesses are examined. The size of unachievable opportunities decreases as understanding of talents and flaws becomes clearer. Threats can be neutralized by taking advantage of favorable circumstances, and organizational strengths can be exploited to compensate for deficiencies.

METHODOLOGY

1. Research Type

A qualitative approach is applied in the author's research model. Qualitative research places an emphasis on the fact that reality is multidimensional, dynamic, and a flow of social experiences that are understood by people (Hardani et al., 2020). The goal of qualitative research is to comprehend social phenomena from the viewpoint of the participant (Siyoto & Sodik, 2015). Participants are those who are asked to be interviewed, observe, or provide information, comments, or thoughts. In-depth interviews, documents, direct observation, participatory observations, and other interactive procedures are used in qualitative research to analyze individuals'

points of view. Because the author will fully describe the occurrences that occur in the field, the sort of research uses descriptive approaches.

A qualitative approach is a research method that generates descriptive data from people and everything noticed from their behavior in the form of words (Suryana & Bayu, 2014). By using inductive reasoning, this qualitative technique seeks to develop a thorough understanding of a certain phenomenon.

2. Research Instrument

Interviews, questionnaires, and documentation studies were the instruments utilized to measure the variables in this study.

3. Data Analysis

The methodical identification of various aspects for a company's strategy is known as a SWOT analysis. Based on logic, this study can identify strengths and opportunities while minimizing flaws and risks. (Rangkuti, 2013). The creation of the company's mission, objectives, strategies, and policies will always be a factor in the strategy-making process. Strategic planning should therefore evaluate the firm's strategic factors its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in light of the current environment.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The abbreviation "SWOT" stands for Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat, and when applied properly, it is one of the most effective analytical tools. This analysis is used to pinpoint the elements that make up a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, and problems that exist in both its internal and external environment. Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS Matrix) Internal analysis is done to determine the strengths that will be used and the anticipated shortcomings. The IFAS matrix (internal factor analysis summary) was used to evaluate the factors. The following are the elements that make Amaaraa.id strong and weak:

Power (Strength)

1. Products that are diverse and fashion-forward.
2. The cost is fairly reasonable. The cheap pricing range for Amaaraa.id's clothing includes shirts starting at Rp. 110,000 and going up to Rp. 150,000.
3. Be sincere and welcoming to clients and potential customers. A vendor must be truthful in how they present their goods, not hide any flaws, and be upfront about the fabric type while still being amiable and quick to answer to chat requests.
4. Offer a discount or price cut to customers. The promotion of a product that offers a price decrease will encourage customers to purchase it, increasing their likelihood of doing so because they can benefit from the discounts.
5. Using social media for business to facilitate marketing. Because social media is now accessible throughout the area and encourages customers to buy without having to travel, employing it for business operations can make marketing simpler.

Deficits

1. Regular use of advertising and marketing is not done. The lack of human resources on Amaaraa.id's efforts to make social media marketing and advertising irregular and give the impression that they are dormant.
2. Don't have a physical location that customers may visit Many rivals that sell products and operate stores likewise have a prejudice towards inviting customers to immediately witness the goods they wish to sell. Amaaraa.id has a weakness in that it is only home.
3. Human resources are very needed in running the business. Amaaraa.id only has two people as an administrator of the social media that is managed by Amaaraa.id
4. Do not provide size in the product Products of this enterprise do not have size in product because Amaaraa.id only sells women's clothes only one size is oversize.

Table 1. Matrix IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary)

S	Internal factors	Weight	Ratings	Score
	Strength			
1	A product that varies and follows fashion trends	0.13	4	0.50

2	A relatively affordable price	0.13	4	0.50
3	Be honest and friendly to customers and prospective buyers	0.08	3	0.25
4	Giving consumers a discount or a price discount	0.13	4	0.50
5	Run a business with social media to make marketing easier	0.13	4	0.50
		0.58		2.24
	Weakness	Weight	Ratings	Score
1	Ads and promotions have not been routinely done	0.13	3	0.38
2	Doesn't have an offline store that can be visited	0.08	2	0.17
3	Lack of human resources on Amaaraa.id	0.08	2	0.17
4	Do not provide size in the product	0.13	3	0.38
	Subtotal	0.42		1.08
	Grand Total	1.00		3.32

From the analysis in table 1. IFAS, strengths and weaknesses have a total score of 3.33 Because the total score above 2.5 this means identifying a strong internal position.

External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS)

The external analysis is carried out to develop the opportunity factors that may be exploited and the threat factors that should be avoided. To find out whether the strategy used has responded to the opportunities and threats that exist, the EFAS Matrix (External Factors Analysis summary) is used, as in table2. The following factors are the opportunity and threat of Amaaraa.id:

Opportunity, as to the opportunity as follows:

1. With the advancement of technology, it becomes easier to make promotions that can introduce Amaaraa.id business
2. The price of a more expensive competitor The prices of a higher competitor can be an opportunity for Amaarra.id because the price of Amaaraa products is relatively cheap compared to competitors.
3. Working together with several parties as reseller reseller increases the reach of the market in a region, with reseller and engaging in cooperation to increase the profit.
4. Developing needs of the community needs that are constantly increasing in the world of fashion will be an opportunity for the fashion enterprise because of the fashion trend that becomes a compulsory need of society.

Threats

1. Many of the business that is kind of fashion business in the era now becomes its own attraction for UMKM companies that want to pioneer business in fashion, become its own threat for other fashion entrepreneurs as well as Amaaraa.id.
2. Models are easy to imitate.
3. In the present era, theft of photos on Amaaraa.id business is often done by irresponsible companies that steal photos of products and wear them back in their stores.

Tabel 2. Matrix EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary)

O	External Factor	Weight	Ratings	Score
	Opportunities			
1	Technological advances can have a beneficial impact	0.17	4	0.67
2	The price of the competitor is more expensive	0.17	3	0.50
3	Collaborate with several parties as Ressler	0.17	3	0.50
4	Growth of the need for a relationship	0.11	4	0.44
	Subtotal	0.61		2.11
T	Threats	Weight	Ratings	Score
1	So many kinds of endeavors.	0.17	3	0.50

2	fashion easy imitated	0.11	2	0.22
3	There was photo theft	0.11	3	0.33
Subtotal		0.39		1.06
Grand Total		1		3.17

From the results of the analysis in the tables.2 EFAS, opportunity and threat factors have a score of 3.17.

SWOT matrix

The strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats found in the matrix of external strategy variables are used to form a SWOT matrix. The opportunity and threat from the company's external environment are compared to the company's strengths and weaknesses using the SWOT matrix. The following study was conducted using the SWOT matrices and data from Amaaraa.id's external strategic factors and internal strategy factor tables:

Table 3. Matrix SWOT

<p>IFAS</p> <p>EFAS</p>	<p>Strenght(S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A product that varies and follows fashion trends price cheap 2) Be honest and friendly to customers and prospective buyers 3) Giving consumers a discount or a price discount 4) Run a business with social media to make marketing easier 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ads and promotions have not been routinely done 2) Doesn't have an offline store that can be visited 3) Lack of SDM on Amaaraa.id 4) Do not provide size in the product
<p>Opportunities(O)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Technological advances can have a beneficial impact 2) The price of the competitor is more expensive 3) Collaborate with several parties as reseller 4) Growth of the need for a relationship 	<p>Strategi(SO)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve the quality of Amaaraa.id products. 2. Give an attractive offer through promo or discount. 3. Enhance good relationships with resellers. 4. Improve offline and online services by adding SDM to the venture. 	<p>Strategi(WO)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provides product size. 2. More actively delivering promotions and social media content 3. Adding e-commerce media as a means of marketing 4. Increase the broader promotion network.
<p>Therats(T)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) So many kinds of endeavours. 2) Model easy to copy 3) There was a photo theft. 	<p>Strategi (ST)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Set a competitive price 2. Add the type of product offered 3. Maintain good relationships with parties such as customers and resellers by giving rewards in the form of bonuses / gifts 	<p>Strategi(WT)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More attractive and varied promotions 2. Forming a good relationship with customers 3. Label and copyright permissions on social media content

Source: Premier data after processing (2023)

Based on the analysis of the SWOT matrix table above, the findings of this analysis suggest that a combination of internal and external factors can affect Amaaraa.id's performance.

E.CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion that may be mad based on the study findings mentioned in the preceding chapter include:

1. The fact that Amaaraa.id is in first-quarter condition suggests that the business is in extremely good financial shape as a result of the strong and attractive prospect supporting the adopted strategy. Businesses have excellent prospects, but they also have internal flaws. As a result, the business can modify its current plan to enhance its internal condition.
2. Promotions are frequently held to increase public interest in buying at Amaaraa.id When the existence of the offline store becomes the focal point for customers who want to always shop at the store, establish your own offline store in the heart of Makassar.
3. Increase the number of employees in order to maximize service by expanding marketing through the use of marketing platforms that serve as places to sell and buy goods, such as Bukalapak and Tokopedia.
4. This will broaden the range of products available for marketing and enable faster delivery of consumer orders.

REFERENCES

1. Afrilia, A. M. (2018). Digital marketing sebagai strategi komunikasi pemasaran “waroenk ora umum” dalam meningkatkan jumlah konsumen. *Jurnal Riset Komunikasi*, 1(1), 147–157. <https://doi.org/10.24329/jurkom.v1i1.21>
2. Aini, Q., & Oktafani, F. (2020). Pengaruh pengetahuan kewirausahaan, motivasi berwirausaha dan lingkungan keluarga terhadap minat berwirausaha mahasiswa fakultas komunikasi dan bisnis telkom university. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 17(2), 151–159. <https://doi.org/10.31849/jieb.v17i2.3845>
3. Akrimi, Y., & Khemakem, R. (2012). What Drive Customers to Spread The Word in Sosial Media. *Journal of Marketing Research and Case Studies*.
4. Amstrong, K. (2016). *Principles of Marketing Sixteenth Edition Global Edition*. England: Pearson Education Limited.
5. Anjani, A., Ratnamulyani, I. A., & Kusumadinata, A. A. (2018). Penggunaan Media Komunikasi Whatsapp terhadap Efektivitas Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Komunikatio*, 4(1), 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.30997/jk.v4i1.1211>
6. Assauri, S. (2014). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
7. Assauri, S. (2015). *Manajemen Pemasaran, Cetakan ke-14*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
8. Cahyono, A. S. (2016). Pengaruh media sosial terhadap perubahan sosial masyarakat di Indonesia. *Publiciana*, 9(1), 140–157. <https://doi.org/10.36563/publiciana.v9i1.79>
9. Dharmmesta, B. S., & Handoko, T. H. (2013). *Manajemen pemasaran: analisa perilaku konsumen* (1st ed.). Yogyakarta: BPFE.
10. Fatimah, I., Syam, A., Rakib, M., Rahmatullah, R., & Hasan, M. (2020). Pengaruh Literasi Kewirausahaan dan Peran Orang Tua Terhadap Kesiapan Berwirausaha Mahasiswa Pendidikan Ekonomi Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Negeri Makassar. *Indonesian Journal of Social and Educational Studies*, 1(1), 83–93.
11. Hardani, H., Ustiawaty, J., Utami, E. F., Istiqomah, R. R., Fardani, R. A., Sukmana, D. J., & Auliya, N. H. (2020). *Metode penelitian kualitatif & kuantitatif*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Ilmu.
12. Hermawan, A. (2012). *Komunikasi pemasaran* (A. Maulana (ed.)). Jakarta : Erlangga.
13. Irfan, M. (2014). Efektivitas penggunaan media sosial twitter sebagai media komunikasi pemasaran Strike. *Courier Di Samarinda. EJournal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 2(2).
14. Latief, N. (2019). *Pengaruh media sosial instagram terhadap omzet penjualan handphone pada dp store Makassar*. Universitas Negeri Makassar.
15. Rakib, M. (2016). Model Komunikasi Wirausaha, Pembelajaran Wirausaha, Sikap Kewirausahaan, dan Kinerja Usaha Kecil. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 17(2).
16. Rakib, M., Tawe, A., Azis, M., Syam, A., & Sanusi, D. A. (2020). Determinants of entrepreneurial intention: Empirical study of student entrepreneurs. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 26(3), 1–12.
17. Rakib, M., Yunus, M., & Amin MT, N. (2018). Creative industry development based on entrepreneurship training in developing local economy in parepare city. *Jurnal OIKOS*, 2(1), 32–46.

18. Rangkuti, F. (2013). *SWOT–Balanced Scorecard*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
19. Siyoto, S., & Sodik, A. (2015). *Dasar Metodologi Penelitian* (Ayup (ed.)). Sleman: Literasi Media Publishing.
20. Sumarsid, S., & Paryanti, A. B. (2022). Pengaruh Kualitas Layanan Dan Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan Pada Grabfood (Studi Wilayah Kecamatan Setiabudi). *Jurnal Ilmiah M-Progress*, 12(1), 70–83. <https://doi.org/0.35968/m-pu.v12i1.867>
21. Suryana, S., & Bayu, K. (2014). *Kewirausahaan: Kiat dan Proses menuju Sukses*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
22. Syam, A. (2017). *Pengaruh pembelajaran kewirausahaan, motivasi, dan minat berwirausaha terhadap pengambilan keputusan berwirausaha mahasiswa di Universitas Negeri Makassar*. Universitas Negeri Makassar.
23. Untari, D., & Fajariana, D. E. (2018). Strategi pemasaran melalui media sosial instagram (studi deskriptif pada akun@subur_batik). *Widya Cipta: Jurnal Sekretari Dan Manajemen*, 2(2), 271–278. <https://doi.org/10.31294/widyacipta.v2i2.4387>
24. Varadarajan, R. (2015). Strategic marketing, marketing strategy and market strategy. *AMS Review*, 5, 78–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13162-015-0073-9>
25. Widagdha, P. A., Fathoni, A., & Malik, D. (2018). Strategi Peningkatan Volume Penjualan Obat Generik Melalui Analisis Swot (Studi Kasus Pada Pt. Bernofarm Pharmaceutical Semarang). *Journal of Management*, 4(4), 1–16.

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